

Deliverable D5.3

First stable BiImage Zoo Model format, software tools, libraries and reference examples

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
DL	Deep Learning
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
JDLL	Java Deep Learning Library
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
PU	Public
RDF	Resource Description File
RI	Research Infrastructure
spec	Specification
v	Version

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Executive Summary

AI4Life is dedicated to democratizing access to modern AI methods in biological imaging, building bridges between life science and computer vision researchers to expand the reach of cutting-edge techniques. A pivotal component of broadening this access involves establishing unified and standardized formats for AI models that can be leveraged across different platforms and tools, including Fiji/ImageJ, CellProfiler, Ilastik, ZeroCostDL4Mic, and ImJoy.

The work described in this deliverable focuses on the creation of the BioImage Model Zoo file format, software tools, and libraries, aligning with the vision to enable seamless model implementation and collaboration. These standards were carefully curated with input from community experts in AI, neural network architecture, data management, and software development, and were put to the test using various deep learning frameworks and programming languages.

We have meticulously designed the model description files to contain sufficient information for consumer software to load the model, and perform model inference, pre-processing, and post-processing. Furthermore, the files have been developed to be extendable and version-controlled, with the ease of sharing in mind.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is a part of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, initiated in September 2022 and set to continue until September 2025. AI4Life's primary mission is to democratize AI-based image analysis for life scientists, revolutionizing the biological imaging field by fostering compatibility, reusability, and efficiency of deep learning (DL) models across diverse platforms.

In recent years, the advancement of innovative DL methodologies has transformed microscopy image restoration and segmentation. However, this exciting growth has exposed challenges related to the reusability, reproducibility, and interoperability of DL models, often confined to specific tools and limiting their cross-compatibility.

To address these challenges, this deliverable focuses on **Objective 5.2**, which aims to develop a common model description file format along with software libraries, tools, and reference examples. This model description file standard is more than a technical solution; it represents a fundamental shift towards enabling seamless interactions between various platforms and tools, including leading-edge technologies like Fiji/ImageJ, ImJoy, ZeroCostDL4Mic, and QuPath.

The importance of this common model description file format cannot be overstated:

- **Interoperability:** The standardization ensures that DL models are not siloed within individual tools, promoting cross-compatibility and flexibility within different microscopy image analysis pipelines.
- **Reusability and Reproducibility:** By encapsulating essential model metadata, the format facilitates the effortless reuse and replication of models across platforms, bolstering the scientific rigor of bioimage analysis.
- **Collaboration and Innovation:** By fostering an environment where developers and users can easily contribute, the common format sets the stage for enhanced collaboration, driving forward innovation and creating a new paradigm of scientific exploration.

Supported by existing deep learning-enabled bioimage analysis software tools and platforms, the [Biolmage Model Zoo](#) stands at the forefront of a new era. The standardized metadata formats not only enrich existing tools but also catalyze the next generation of bioimage analysis. AI4Life's ambition extends beyond creating a repository, aiming to lay the foundation for a future where the life science community can leverage AI models in an interoperable, reusable, and innovative way.

2. Description of work

The AI4Life project's primary goal is to establish a robust, unified repository that serves the needs of the entire microscopy image analysis community. The work is designed to support the democratization and standardization of deep learning models, fostering accessibility and efficiency across various platforms.

2.1 The BioImage Model Description File Format

The BioImage Model Zoo's creation is dependent on the intricate development of the Resource Description File (RDF) formats stored in YAML files. These RDFs define the essential structure and details of the resources, enabling the Zoo to present, test, and execute them systematically. The categorization into different RDF types allows for comprehensive organization.

2.1.1 General RDF

The General RDF is a YAML file that serves as the backbone of our specification. It encapsulates vital details such as name, description, authors, and citations (detailed specification [here](#)). An empowering feature is the inclusion of arbitrary fields within the 'config' field, allowing the specification of additional metadata information that may not be part of our current RDF specification but enables further exploitation of the Zoo's content. For resources like models and collections, the general RDF can be extended to include the minimal technical information required for cross-compatibility and deployment in consumer software.

2.1.2 Model RDF

The Model RDF (detailed specification [here](#)) is designed to describe trained neural networks meticulously. Key features include:

- **Weights Field:** Specifies the location of network weight files, supporting formats like Keras HDF5, ONNX, PyTorch state dictionary, Tensorflow Javascript, Tensorflow Saved Model Bundle, and Torchscript.
- **Inputs and Outputs Fields:** Describes the input and output tensors of the model, including data type, shape, axis types, and order, with a restriction to specific spatial and batch axes.
- **Transformations:** Defined preprocessing for 'inputs' and postprocessing for 'outputs', allowing the model to adapt to different data types and formats.
- **Test Inputs and Outputs:** Ensures that the model runs as expected and includes optional sample inputs and outputs for hands-on illustration.

- Training Documentation: Contains information on how the model was trained, and may link to other bioimage.io resources for reproduction or refinement.

2.1.3 Collection RDF

The Collection RDF is a sophisticated construct that conveniently describes a group of resources. The specification is available [here](#). Key characteristics include:

- Collection Field: Holds a list where each entry represents an independent RDF, facilitating unique identification and linkage.
- Unique Identifier Requirement: Each collection and entry must have a unique identifier (e.g., id: 'ilastik/torch-em-3d-unet-notebook'), ensuring that nested collections have distinctive resource identifiers.

This strategic categorization into General, Model, and Collection RDFs ensures that every detail of the models, from metadata to weights to specific input-output transformations, is meticulously captured. These formats foster interoperability, robustness, and adaptability, setting the stage for seamless integration and utilization across various platforms and applications. By defining these specifications, we enable a unified way of describing and consuming trained DL models, paving the way for a more collaborative and innovative microscopy image analysis community.

2.2 Software Libraries, Tools, and Reference Examples

Our work also includes various implementations of the model zoo file format (RDF).

Python Libraries

We provide two Python libraries for conveniently interacting with models.

bioimageio.spec: A Python library that defines the different RDFs using marshmallow. It facilitates validation, automatic upgrade, and update functionalities, streamlining the creation of high-quality metadata. The spec library is available at: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/spec-bioimage-io>.

bioimageio.core: An advanced library that offers nuanced interactions with models. It enables prediction, model testing, and conversion between selected weight formats. This library is a pivotal tool used by Python-based consumer software like ilastik, the StarDist Python library, ZeroCostDL4Mic, and BioEngine Apps. The core library is available at: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/core-bioimage-io-python>.

Java Libraries

JDLL: Java Deep Learning Library provides a Java implementation for consuming models in the bioimage.io RDF format agnostically, enabling communication between Java software and various Deep Learning frameworks (engines). It also allows the use of multiple DL frameworks in the same session, manages the different DL frameworks, and brings the models from the Bioimage.io repository to Java. JDLL is able to load models and make inferences, create tensors, download Bioimage.io models, and manage the supported DL frameworks. The library is designed in a modular way, allowing the main software to avoid dealing with the various objects and structures required by different DL frameworks. Instead, the Java model runner provides interfaces for models and tensors that handle internally their creation and inference in the different Java engines. The main software only needs to interact with the Java model runner and does not need to worry whether the model is in PyTorch, Tensorflow, or another framework. The source code of this library is available at: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/JDLL>.

Tools and example models

As of now, the RDF format is already supported by existing software bioimage analysis software and platforms, including ilastik, deeplmageJ, ImJoy, StarDist, ZeroCostDL4Mic, and QuPath. These tools can access around 50 models in the bioimage model zoo: <https://bioimage.io>. These models also serve as reference examples for the model description file formats. A json summary of these available models is provided at: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/collection-bioimage-io/blob/gh-pages/collection.json>.

To enable FAIR access to the models, resources defined by the RDF are hosted either on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) or in dedicated GitHub repositories under the bioimage-io organization (<https://github.com/bioimage-io>).

The above-mentioned libraries and tools represent our commitment to offering seamless integration, minimal coding, and robust standardization of model execution across various tools and frameworks. Through our strategic alignment with existing deep learning-enabled bioimage analysis tools, the AI4Life project fortifies a new paradigm of scientific exploration, fostering collaboration, and nurturing the next generation of bioimage analysis.

3. Conclusion

AI4Life is steadfast in its commitment to democratizing access to state-of-the-art AI methods in bioimaging, nurturing connections between life science and computer vision specialists to proliferate avant-garde approaches. A cornerstone of this democratization is the establishment of unified, standardized, and comprehensive formats for AI models

to bridge different platforms and tools, including but not limited to Fiji/ImageJ, Ilastik, ZeroCostDL4Mic, QuPath, and ImJoy.

The work detailed in this deliverable revolves around the inception of the BioImage Model Zoo, encompassing not just a unique file format but also an extensive array of software tools, libraries, and model description files. These standards have been thoughtfully curated, leveraging insights from community experts in AI, neural network architecture, data management, and software development, and thoroughly examined through various deep learning frameworks and programming languages. Beyond the creation of the BioImage Model Zoo, we have meticulously devised model description files to encompass the essentials for consumer software to load the model, and perform model inference, pre-processing, and post-processing. These files are crafted to be both extendable and version-controlled, with a distinct focus on facilitating seamless sharing, fostering collaboration, and aligning with the overarching vision of streamlined model implementation and interoperability across the microscopy image analysis community.

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